

ACUTE PHLEGMONOUS GASTRITIS – CASE REPORT

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Starting from a surgically resolved case, the paper provides an updated analysis of the mechanisms, clinical features, and diagnostic considerations for acute phlegmonous gastritis, along with possible therapeutic solutions.

Keywords: phlegmonous gastritis, surgical treatment

1. INTRODUCTION

Acute phlegmonous gastritis (AGF) is a rare condition, characterized mainly by severe bacterial invasion of the gastric wall. The clinical manifestations of AGF are nonspecific: abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, fever and signs of infection. Early diagnosis is difficult, given that the disease develops rapidly, progressing to necrosis of the gastric wall and peritonitis. Therefore, diagnosis is delayed or ignored, and AGF has a high mortality rate. If before the era of antibiotics, the mortality rate reached 92%, with antibiotic therapy, the mortality rate decreased to 48%. However, immediate surgical intervention remains necessary to improve the prognosis, when antibiotic treatment is ineffective. The paper presents a case of AGF, diagnosed and treated in our department.

2. CASE REPORT

A 56-year-old woman admission, presenting with epigastric pain, fever (39-40°C) and vomiting, for 4 days, with worsening in the last 24 hours. From the anamnesis, moderate constant ethanol consumption was noted, a so-called old gastric ulcer, without regular treatment and an acute respiratory infection (about 2 weeks ago), treated with oral and symptomatic anti-inflammatories, but which had not completely resolved. On the recommendation of the family doctor, the patient administered Zinnat (cefuroxime), but the situation did not improve, and even worsened, in the last hours, which is why she was sent to the hospital.

Upon admission, she presented with fever 39.2°C, tachycardia 126/min, with blood pressure within normal limits 130/80 mmHg. Physical examination revealed dyspnea and muscular defense, predominantly in the upper abdominal area. Laboratory tests: leukocytes 6500/mm³, with neutrophils 88%. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) revealed that the entire gastric wall was thickened, due to edema, without signs of perforation.

Antibiotic – Tienam (imipenem/cilastatin), antacids, analgesics and rehydration were administered, obtaining a slight improvement, after which the abdominal pain intensified, vomiting with a purulent tinge was repeated. Median supraumbilical laparotomy revealed: cloudy-purulent perigastric fluid; the stomach wall presented necrotic - nigrescent areas, at the body and antrum level. A 4/5 gastrectomy was decided and performed, followed by reconstruction by gastrojejunal

anastomosis on a Y-loop, and double peritoneal drainage – subhepatic and of the Douglas pouch. The peritoneal fluid sample was sent to the laboratory for culture and antibiogram. Under intensive treatment, continuing the initiated antibiotic therapy, the postoperative evolution was favorable, with discharge cured after 10 days.

3. DISCUSSION

GAF was originally described by Cruveilhier in the early 18th century and, in the last 50 years, an average of 1 case/year has occurred. The disease can affect all age groups, but is more common in adults over 50 years of age, with a male-female ratio of 2:1. Although rare, especially after the use of antibiotics, GAF becomes urgent and develops rapidly once it appears. With the high mortality of this disease, early recognition and immediate action are crucial. With <500 cases reported in the literature, it requires the attention of medical personnel.

Even now, the etiopathogenesis of GAF is not completely elucidated, the cause being considered to be bacterial suppuration, which invades the stomach. Hemolytic streptococcus is found in about 70% of cases, followed by Staphylococcus aureus, Pneumococcus and Enterococcus. Bacterial invasion of the gastric wall can be facilitated by a gastric ulcer or chronic gastritis. Pathogenic bacteria of the pharynx can directly affect the damaged mucosa, but also a respiratory tract infection or other infection, with pathogenic bacteria, that penetrate the gastric wall via the blood or lymphatic route. Alcohol consumption, malnutrition and advanced age are favorable conditions. In the presented case, the patient had as a predisposing factor long-term alcohol consumption, probably a pre-existing gastritis and had not fully recovered from the recent respiratory tract infection. Considering that hemolytic streptococcus was cultured from peritoneal fluid collected intraoperatively, we assumed that the GFA was caused by this pathogen, common for respiratory infections.

We can imagine that the pathophysiological process begins with the bacterial invasion of the submucosa, which then propagate and diffuse into the mucosa, muscularis and serosa. Two types of microbial invasion of the stomach are described: diffuse and localized, depending on the interval of the lesion.

- the diffuse type is more frequent clinically and presents a dark red gastric wall, with diffuse thicken-

ing; when the stomach wall is squeezed, pus is discharged. This type can also cause the extension of the lesion, with perforation of the gastric wall, in severe circumstances.

- the localized type presents hyperemia and erosion of the gastric mucosa, ulceration, necrosis or bleeding.

The localized type is associated with a lower mortality rate than the diffuse type (10%:55%). In our patient, the stomach wall was obviously thickened, and necrosis was found on the entire circumference of the gastric body and antrum; perigastrically there was a tendency for an abscess to form. Therefore, this case belonged to the diffuse type.

Early diagnosis of AGF is difficult, due to the non-specific nature of its clinical manifestations, including acute abdomen syndrome, sudden onset of abdominal pain, high fever and chills, nausea and vomiting. Thus, differential diagnosis with other conditions belonging to the acute abdomen (e.g. peritonitis due to perforation of a hollow organ, acute cholecystitis, acute pancreatitis) is necessary. With the development of the disease, fever may increase, signs of peritoneal irritation become evident and vomiting may become purulent. Abdominal CT usually finds the characteristic features of GAF: thickening of the gastric wall, areas of low intensity within the gastric wall (abscess) and gas accumulation. The patient's clinical presentation included abdominal pain, epigastric peritonitis and characteristic CT. In the presented case, purulent vomiting and CT examination were defining for the positive diagnosis of GAF, distinguishing it from other entities of the acute abdomen.

Acute GAF has a high mortality rate, and the key to successful treatment is early diagnosis and treatment. Before the advent of antibiotics, the mortality rate was 83% to 92%, and the mortality rate has decreased to 48% even after antibiotics became available. In addition, nutritional support and rehydration are very important for therapeutic success. However, if conservative treatment is ineffective, surgery should be performed immediately to avoid worsening the disease. The patient's condition worsened after conservative

treatment. Therefore, emergency surgery was performed, with postoperative supportive treatment. The patient eventually recovered.

4. CONCLUSIONS

GAF does not have a specific clinical picture, evolving as an acute abdomen

Abdominal CT is useful for both early diagnosis and detection of complications.

Once APG is detected, antibiotic treatment is important and mandatory, but if this treatment fails, surgery should be performed immediately to improve the prognosis.

Currently, given the use of antibiotics, the incidence rate of GAF is very low. However, once the disease occurs, it progresses rapidly and has an extremely high mortality rate. Therefore, it requires serious attention from clinicians.

References

1. Ramon C., Nemet S., Malka A., Elbirt D. Phlegmonous gastritis: Review of the pathophysiology. *American Journal of the Medical Sciences*, 2024, 367(4):274–277.
2. Alkubaisi MA, Mohammed NK, Ibrahim IS, et al., Phlegmonous gastritis as the first presentation of acute leukemia: A case report. *Cureus*, 2025, 17(4)
3. Müller T., Gmür E., 1. Ramon C., Nemet S., Malka A., Elbirt D. (2024) Phlegmonous gastritis: Review of the pathophysiology. *American Journal of the Medical Sciences*, 2024, 367(4):274–277.
4. Costa C., Antunes I., Lalandia R., et al., Phlegmonous gastritis: An under-recognised rapidly fatal condition. *European Journal of Case Reports in Internal Medicine*, 2025, 12
5. Prasad A., Benjamin G., Joseph A., Mangalanandan S., When gastric inflammation turns deadly: insights into acute phlegmonous gastritis — a case report. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 2025, 13(08):1282–1284.
6. Yakami Y., et al., Phlegmonous gastritis: a case series. *J Med Case Reports*, 2021, 15:445 Phlegmonous gastritis with streptococcal toxic shock syndrome after endoscopy.